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Impact of Organizational Culture on Employee Satisfaction: A Case of Hilton Hotel, United Kingdom

Christine Reidhead¹

¹ Assistant Professor of Business, Navajo Technical University, USA. Email: creidhead@navajotech.edu

Abstract

Purpose: This paper has focused on examining the impact of organizational culture on employee satisfaction in Hotel Hilton, United Kingdom. **Design:** The paper is written on the basis of secondary data. The research study is conducted on the basis of qualitative research method and data is collected through critical review of literature from secondary sources. The secondary data is collected from scholarly articles and books. **Findings:** From the findings, it is revealed that there is a significant impact of organizational culture on employee satisfaction. When, the management of an organization focuses highly on providing supportive organizational culture, then, it helps in enhancing the satisfaction level of employees. The satisfied employees in an organization serve as a competitive advantage. **Research Limitations:** Due to lack of enough time and resources, the paper is written on the basis of one case study, so, this might decrease the generalizability of research findings. Moreover, future studies can be conducted for examining the importance of organizational culture for other important factors of the firm. **Practical Implications:** The findings of this research paper proves to be much beneficial for managers of organizations, as they can get to know that how satisfaction level of employees can be enhanced through focusing on organizational culture. **Originality:** Previously, there was no study conducted for exploring the importance of organizational culture for enhancing employee satisfaction, and how it could be directly linked to the competitive advantage of the firm. So, this study has been carried out to investigate the impact of organizational culture on employee satisfaction, in the case of Hilton Hotel UK.

Keywords: Organizational Culture, Employee Satisfaction, Hilton Hotel

1. Introduction

In the hospitality industry, human resource plays a key role in ensuring long term survival and success of the firm. Nowadays, it has become highly important to establish that type of organizational culture, with the help of which effective human resource management can be ensured. The establishment of supportive organizational culture has become important, for the purpose of maintaining a good position in the market. It is significant to establish that organizational culture, through which maximum support and continuous improvement can be provided by the firm. The long term growth of an organization depends on the culture of the firm, because this has a significant influence on employee commitment as well as retention in the firm (Arifin, 2015). When there is flexibility in the organization, the work environment will provide employees with a cohesive work place, as well as, independence without feeling any kind of burden. As the business operations of a hotel mainly depend on employees, it is important to provide that culture to employees, in which they can work with full commitment

and dedication (Braithwaite et al, 2017). When employees have a complete understanding of an organizational culture, it ultimately results in improving their performance.

Organizational culture is basically a set of various value systems that can help a firm. With the help of a supportive organizational culture, employees get a better understanding of all key functions of the firm, through sharing key norms and values (Belias et al, 2015). The success of Hotel Hilton, United Kingdom (UK), depends on its effective management of human resource, as a result, becomes a key part in the organizational culture. However, Hilton Hotel is facing a lack of satisfaction among employees, hence, creating a need for exploring and revealing to the employees the importance of organizational culture. Previously, there was no study conducted for exploring the importance of organizational culture for enhancing employee satisfaction, and how it could be directly linked to the competitive advantage of the firm. So, this study has been carried out to investigate the impact of organizational culture on employee satisfaction, in the case of Hilton Hotel UK.

1.1. Research Aim

The aim is to explore the impact of organizational culture on employee satisfaction in the hospitality industry of UK.

1.2. Research Objectives

- To analyze the importance of organizational culture of hotel industry.
- To explore the role-played by employee satisfaction in an organization.
- To understand the influence of organizational culture on employee satisfaction in the hospitality industry.
- To understand how satisfied employees, serve as a source of a competitive advantage.

2. Organizational Culture

Based on the definition provided by Kontoghiorghes (2016), it is stated that, "organizational culture is a combination of values, beliefs, working styles, and associations that differentiate one enterprise from the other." Jung and Yoon (2015) stated that corporate culture in every organization is based mostly on psychological effects that enable researchers to understand how employees in the company think about their organization. It also informs researchers on how organizational culture influences the decisions of employees. Researchers also claim that different levels of organizational culture are centered on the different organizational principles, traditions, practices and past stories. Organizational culture is a set of shared values that allows organizations to understand that employees embrace a similar organizational culture, though, with diverse backgrounds within the organization. Han et al (2015) defined the term "normative glue" as organizational culture, which simply means that organizational culture holds together all the organizational processes. Organizational culture has affected the internal corporate practices and how employees are influenced and engaged towards the values and goals of the organization. It enhances the employees' desire to routinely please the customer repeatedly, therefore, encouraging the customer to return to make more purchases. Guiso et al (2015) states that organizational culture influences different people in different ways, as they think and make decisions consciously and subconsciously, based on what they interpret and feel, and eventually act upon it. According to Balkar (2015), it is possible to maintain and also influence management actions and trusty climate by the instability in the economic system and high individualism. As a result, these actions may inflict a negative impact on the valued work displayed by the employees. If an organizational culture causes issues such as, internal difficulties, the diversified group of that organization is responsible for it.

3. Employee Satisfaction

Job satisfaction seems to be a very interesting subject concerning the organizational behavior of the organization. According to Taneja et al (2015), job satisfaction is an analysis of the assessment level of the individual about how the workplace environment fulfills its demands. The satisfied employees will work for the growth and

advancement of the organization and will put forth every effort to make its organizational culture healthy. Several researchers stated that job satisfaction is essential for employee motivation (Aldridge and Fraser, 2016; McFadden et al, 2015). Some evidence suggests that if workers are satisfied with their job performance, their productivity with the organization becomes greater. Thus, it results in strong employee engagement with the organization. If the personnel have a positive mental attitude toward work, it could be because they are comfortable and satisfied with their work. Hanaysha (2016) in his recent research pointed out that job satisfaction does have a positive effect on employee engagement and is negatively related to employee turnover. According to Dekoulou and Trivellas (2015), job satisfaction is linked through organizational function to the self-actualization needs of employee fulfillment. Several studies show a direct and healthy relationship between customer satisfaction and job satisfaction. Several studies gave different kinds of metrics about this relationship, and Abouraia and Othman (2017) gave the analysis of this positive relationship between job satisfaction and business success. According to Bergheim et al (2015) job satisfaction is a blend of physiological, psychological, and environmental situations through which an individual can confess to being satisfied with the job.

Job satisfaction is an alignment that is quite effective for the part of an individual towards their roles of work. Zumrah and Boyle (2015) - while defining job satisfaction said that job satisfaction is the process through which the employees view their jobs and its various aspects. Employment satisfaction reflects individual behavior, where they do their job. Job satisfaction also indicates commitment and satisfaction of employees with the job. Job satisfaction is a fundamental aspect that determines the direction employees gravitate towards when speaking of appreciation, pay, advancement, and achievement of the goals that satisfy their desires. According to Nie et al (2015) individuals possess different attitudes regarding their job, including the different sorts of jobs that their boss, supervisor, and wages do.

4. Supportive Organizational Culture and Employee Satisfaction

Every organization in the hotel industry has a culture, whether it's deliberately introduced or not. Some organizational cultures seem to be more welcoming than others, and that is an intriguing study that needs answers. Scholars such as Tanwar and Prasad (2016) and Mas-Machuca et al (2016) broadly conceptualized supporting organizational culture as a cohesive set of beliefs, values, expectations, and behaviors among the employees of the organization. Such authors, further described by demonstrating the omnipresence of common beliefs, values, assumptions, and practices as well as the degree to which their members' different values, beliefs, expectations and practices are consistent. Some supporters also claim that the organization continues to benefit from a positive and widespread organizational culture as it fosters engagement, enthusiasm, unity, identity, and uniformity that turn to promote job satisfaction for employees. Hotel culture is mainly based on cognitive systems that explain the way in which workers think and make judgments. Manojlovich and Ketefian (2016) argued that organizational culture is a common set of values and standards expressed within an organization by individuals and groups. For them, the company culture governs how workers communicate with each other and with non-organization stakeholders.

Organizational culture is the importance of structures and expectations that govern the way the company handles its business. This indicates that the values and culture of the company impact profoundly on all those who connected to the organization. It was also clarified that the standards are intangible, but if the company wants to improve employee performance and productivity, then standards must be their first concern to deal with. Contrary to the above evaluation, Chordiya et al (2017) argues that supporting culture may sometimes lead to unconstrained employee demand from the company which can become a hurdle to employee adaptation and transition. Singh et al (2016) further clarifies that positive culture in hotels such as compensation and rewards, opportunities for growth, training, communication and administrative support can often contribute to a change in objectives. Karanika-Murray et al. (2017) claims that the culture of encouragement will move the focus of workers from their organizational goals to their personal growth and benefits. Joo and Lee (2017) further added that if cultural standards and ways of doing things become more important, then the primary purpose of the organization may be overshadowed. Despite the above contrasting evaluation, Sonyand Mekoth (2016) still believe that promoting culture such as rewards and benefits, incentives for contact, supervisory support, and

training and development is a progressive source for employee satisfaction as well as a source of competitive advantage for an organization. However, he argues that each modern culture in organizations should be welcoming and supportive but restricted to certain circumstances. According to Ilyas and Abdullah (2016) job satisfaction is an internally and externally characteristic in which the strong culture of such an organization is focused on the general assessment by an employee of how happy he/she is on the job. Thus, a strong and healthy culture of hotel companies improves self-confidence among its employees and reduces work stress. Tekingündüz et al (2017) believes that effective workplace preparation promotes dedication and strengthens the ethical behavior of the workers within the organization. It is vehemently argued by Singh et al (2016) that if the core value of an organization is not properly defined, conveyed or generally accepted by those working for the company then weak organizational culture may arise. This happens often when there is little harmony between the manner in which things are done and the beliefs inherited. It usually results in poor employee behavior that then results in poor customer experience.

5. Satisfied Employees as Source of Competitive Edge

Hiring the best employees for the Hotel Company does not guarantee success. Nevertheless, recruiting and cultivating competent employees through successful principles of culture such as interaction, encouragement, opportunities for growth and supervisory support will guarantee and give the company a competitive advantage over its rivals. If workers are happy with the organizational culture, they're fulfilled and will certainly support selling the business to outsiders. Islam et al (2015) in his studies acknowledged that the satisfaction of the workforce is defined and influenced by the organizational culture. He added that motivated workers would ensure organizational success by performing wholeheartedly and selflessly giving the company a competitive edge over their rivals. Nazarian et al (2017) thinks that the different forms of communication within the organization as well as the relationship between the employer and the employee have a positive impact on the way in which employees conduct their daily routines at work.

The model of organizational culture assessment established by Nie et al (2015) on employee satisfaction as a key source of competitive advantage measures the relation between organizational structure and job satisfaction. Such two researchers found that workers at various levels of employment are affected by different aspects of work and different dimensions of the work environment. Taneja et al (2015) continued that communication channels and working conditions greatly impact employee satisfaction and send exceptional signal to outside customers. The manner through which the employer treats workers at work can shed a positive effect on the competitive advantage of the organization. Aggrieved and unsatisfied employees do not have time to explain products and services to customers. Losing one single customer per day can cost the company seven customers within one week. Schuster et al (2016) says that employee satisfaction and job performance are linked with organizational culture. He says that culture and job satisfaction are interdependent and seem to have a strong impact on the competitive advantage of the organization. Based on this, Zumrah and Boyle (2015) argue that company management with positive culture can improve employee work efficiency, engagement, and satisfaction. There is a close relationship between organizational culture and job satisfaction. Researchers demonstrate that a strong organization will generate job satisfaction for employees. On the contrary, certain dimensions reflect hostile relations and other positive relationships. Their theory is that the workers perceive cultural values and individuality as contingent for the varied relationships. It should be remembered that not all organizational cultures create competitiveness unless it meets the standards of employees and customers.

Schuster et al (2016) argued that if workers are well content with the culture of the organization, they will be motivated to work tirelessly to boost the business performance over their rivals. From their perspective, the duties of the employee are clear, which would inevitably boost the organizational performance level. Mas-Machuca et al (2016) reported in their research that each positive organizational culture will increase employee satisfaction and will lower organizational turnover ratio. Although, all companies have a culture but any company that does not incorporate encouraging and compensatory cultural traits, such as, incentives for professional development, training and supervisory support, their workers are not as engaged in a well-mannered way. The effects of alienated and unengaged workers will adversely affect the competitive advantage of the company. This is because disgruntled workers wouldn't necessarily do their best to see the company get ahead

and surpass their rivals. Employees satisfied with the organizational culture will affect the willingness of other employees to provide professional services which reflects superior management support.

6. Conclusion

In the end, it is the organizational culture that is considered highly important for organizations in the hospitality and hotel industry, for employees to perform and excel at a higher standard than the average organization when speaking of employee performance and commitment level. When employees have a complete understanding about the culture of a firm, they feel satisfied with their job. Employee satisfaction is the emotional capacity linked with both, positive, as well as, negative elements, to every job experience. An employee shows high levels of commitment, when the organizational culture fully supports him or her, and, also results in increasing the chance of fulfilling organizational goals. With the continuous willingness of commitment from the employees, it strengthens their employment outlook with the organization. There is a significant impact on employee satisfaction and the employees' intention of whether to leave or stay in the organization when the determining factor is the organization's culture.

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